

Male Mouse 1



Male Rat 1



● Rostral 1 ● Rostral 2 ● Caudal 1 ● Caudal 2

Male Mouse 2



Male Rat 2



● Rostral 1 ● Rostral 2 ● Caudal 1 ● Caudal 2

Male Mouse 3



Male Rat 3



● Rostral 1 ● Rostral 2 ● Caudal 1 ● Caudal 2

Male Mouse 4



Male Rat 4



● Rostral 1 ● Rostral 2 ● Caudal 1 ● Caudal 2

Male Mouse 5



Male Rat 5



● Rostral 1 ● Rostral 2 ● Caudal 1 ● Caudal 2

Male Mouse 6



Male Rat 6



● Rostral 1 ● Rostral 2 ● Caudal 1 ● Caudal 2

All Male Mice



All Male Rats



● Rostral 1 ● Rostral 2 ● Caudal 1 ● Caudal 2

Female Mouse 1



Female Rat 1



● Rostral 1 ● Rostral 2 ● Caudal 1 ● Caudal 2

Female Mouse 2



Female Rat 2



● Rostral 1 ● Rostral 2 ● Caudal 1 ● Caudal 2

Female Mouse 3



Female Rat 3



● Rostral 1 ● Rostral 2 ● Caudal 1 ● Caudal 2

Female Mouse 4



Female Rat 4



● Rostral 1 ● Rostral 2 ● Caudal 1 ● Caudal 2

Female Mouse 5



Female Rat 5



● Rostral 1 ● Rostral 2 ● Caudal 1 ● Caudal 2

Female Mouse 6



Female Rat 6



● Rostral 1 ● Rostral 2 ● Caudal 1 ● Caudal 2

All Female Mice



All Female Rats



● Rostral 1 ● Rostral 2 ● Caudal 1 ● Caudal 2

All Mice



All Rats



● Rostral 1 ● Rostral 2 ● Caudal 1 ● Caudal 2